

**THE ROLE OF ADVANCED TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH
IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION**

Safarova Z. G.

independent researcher

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinflarda ingliz tilini o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsiyalar usullarni qo'llash natijasida, o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatlari rivojlanishi, nutqi ravonlashishi, tez va to'g'ri javob berish malakasi shakllanishi, bilimga ishtiyoq uyg'otishi, darslarga puxta hozirlik ko'rishga intilishi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Bu orqali ta'limning innovatsion texnologiyalaridan foydalanishga imkoniyat tug'iladi va talab ortadi. Hozirgi kunda o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni chet tillariga o'qitish sifatini ta'minlash, chet tillarida erkin so'zlasha oladigan mutaxassislarni tayyorlash tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish, chet tillarni o'zlashtirish orqali jahon ta'lim standartlariga javob beradigan yetuk kadrlarni tayyorlash yurtimizda amalga oshirilayotgan ta'lim islohotining maqsadlaridan biridir.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy, innovatsiya, boshlang'ich, o'yin, ta'limiy, ta'lim

Abstract: This article presents modern approaches and innovations in teaching English in elementary grades as a result of the application of methods, students develop logical thinking skills, improve speech, form the skill of a quick and correct answer, awaken a passion for knowledge, a desire for thorough preparation for lessons.

This gives access to innovative learning technologies and increases demand. Currently, ensuring the quality of teaching foreign languages to the younger generation, radically improving the system of training specialists who are fluent in foreign languages, training mature personnel who meet international educational standards by mastering foreign languages is one of the goals of the educational reform being carried out in the country.

Keywords: modern, innovative, startup, gaming, educational, education

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены современные подходы и инновации в обучении английскому языку в начальных классах в результате применения методик у учащихся развиваются навыки логического мышления, совершенствуется речь, формируется навык быстрого и правильного ответа, пробуждается страсть к знаниям, стремление к тщательной подготовке к урокам.

Благодаря этому появляется доступ к инновационным технологиям обучения и повышается спрос. В настоящее время обеспечение качества обучения подрастающего поколения иностранным языкам, коренное совершенствование системы подготовки специалистов, свободно владеющих иностранными языками, подготовка зрелых кадров, соответствующих мировым образовательным стандартам, посредством овладения иностранными языками, является одной из целей проводимой в стране образовательной реформы.

Ключевые слова: современный, инновационный, стартап, игровой, образовательный, образование

The integration of Uzbekistan into a single educational space, the process of reforming and modernizing the Uzbek school education system in general and language education in particular have led to a rethinking of the goals, objectives and content of teaching foreign languages, in particular English, which today is the most important communication tool at the international level.

All spheres of our life require knowledge of the English language to one degree or another, and its study is becoming more and more in demand every year. But if in educational institutions the main task of teaching a foreign language is the formation of foreign language communicative competence of students, then after graduation from universities and colleges, the goal may be the need to use the language for professional purposes.

The emergence of the English language for special purposes, as well as many other human activities, is associated with changes in the modern world and its needs.

The era of comprehensive globalization has led to significant changes in the structure of the training of future specialists. The development of high technologies, close scientific and technical ties required new approaches to the formation of a set of competencies, including communicative and socio-cultural within the framework of the native language and at least one or two foreign languages.

The term "English for specific purposes" (English for specific purposes or ESP) appeared in the 60s of the XX century in English-speaking countries both as a scientific direction and as a type of English language teaching that meets the needs of students. The direction of specialized English language teaching is one of the fastest growing at the moment. This is reflected in university programs offering a master's course in this field, as well as in the emergence of a huge number of courses for foreign students, scientific communities operate, international conferences are held.

Currently, there are several types of ESP, such as:

1. English for Academic Purposes (English for Academic Purposes) is one of the priority areas of modern language training. The content of this direction is determined, on the one hand, by the practical needs of students related to the implementation of academic and professional tasks, on the other hand, by the requirements imposed by educational programs for the quality of language training. This course includes working with a large number of authentic texts, as well as a variety of exercises and tasks aimed at developing and improving lexical and grammatical skills, practicing language and academic skills. This course is most often used by students around the world, getting a particular profession at the university of their country or abroad.

2. English for work (English for Occupational Purposes). This course implies seminars throughout the year for those who need special language skills to work, since in an ever-changing working environment it is necessary to be able to adapt, gain new knowledge and improve efficiency, increasing employment opportunities with a higher degree of remuneration.

3. English for Business Purposes is in demand among "non-native speakers" of English and is studied for the purpose of doing business with English-speaking

countries or companies located outside the English-speaking world, but which, nevertheless, use English as an international language. In such cases, the object of the exercise is effective communication. The strict rules of grammar in such cases are sometimes ignored, for example, when the sole purpose of the negotiator is to reach the fastest possible agreement.

4. English for Professional Purposes (English for Professional Purposes) involves increasing skills in oral and written English, with the aim of confident self-expression and potential advancement in professional conditions. For example, this course is often necessary for doctors to study and implement new technologies, as well as due to the fact that most of the medical literature and terminology have Latin designations.

5. English for tourist purposes (English for Vacational Purposes). This course is specifically designed to help professionals in the international tourism industry improve their communication skills in English as well as their international tourism methods. This course will give students a broader understanding of the international tourism sector, as well as equip them with useful skills when working with clients. In addition, this course opens up the boundaries of communication for an ordinary tourist at every stage of their journey anywhere in the world.

6. English for Aviation is an English language specially designed to teach English communication skills to pilots and air traffic controllers, as well as to assist them in achieving and maintaining operational level 4 (now this is a requirement of the International Civil Aviation Organization). Aviation English also includes the so-called language of flight (the language of a flight), which contains about three hundred words and is a combination of professional "jargon" and simple English. (For example: approach – landing; mayday – a message about a life-threatening alarm; pan–pan – a message about a non–life-threatening alarm; standby - standby mode; wilco - formed from "will comply" means that the pilot has received the message and will follow it; and much more). This vocabulary was created in order to prevent pilots and air traffic controllers from misunderstanding each other due to incorrect pronunciation, which could potentially lead to a fatal accident.

For our research, it is of interest to study the peculiarities of the English language for special purposes in the field of tourism and hospitality, as well as the specifics of its teaching.

At the moment, the tourism sector is one of the most popular. Many graduates choose to work in the field of tourism after graduating from higher educational institutions or receive a second higher education in this specialty. The school English course does not involve obtaining such specific knowledge, therefore this course is intended for students who wish to expand their knowledge of English in such a specialty as tourism.

Twenty years ago, any training was based on the classical methodology, in which most of the time was devoted to the theory of a foreign language. During the lessons, students studied syntactic constructions, new vocabulary, discussed grammatical rules, and also read and translated texts, did written assignments and sometimes listened to audio recordings. The development of conversational skills took only ten percent of the time of the entire class. As a result, the student understood the texts in English and knew the grammatical rules, but could not express his thoughts. That is why there is a radically different approach in the developed ESP course for tourism, in which the maximum amount of time is devoted to the development of communication skills, namely listening and speaking.

Thus, in the course we have developed, we have applied the following techniques:

- Communicative – its main principle is the use of lexical units and grammatical constructions studied in lessons in speech, both oral and written. All classes are developed and conducted in a foreign language or with minimal inclusion of native speech. The teacher only directs students, asks them questions and creates a communicative situation, while 70% of the time of the entire class is spoken by students.

- Project – initially, this method of teaching English was intended for children, but today it has become more relevant for adults with an elementary level of English and especially for those who want to master it to work in the tourism sector. Its meaning is

to use the studied material in practice and is optimal for the organization of knowledge control at the end of the whole module.

- Intensive – this technique has gained particular popularity among those who seek to learn to speak English in the shortest possible time. To achieve this seemingly unrealistic goal allows a high level of language templates and a good basic level of knowledge of the student. Thanks to the study of a large number of stable expressions, their memorization and working out, a student can learn to explain himself in a foreign language and understand the interlocutor in a fairly short time.

In the process of studying the above methods, their impact on the process of organization and effectiveness of training, as well as during the development of the ESP course in tourism, we came to the conclusion that such forms of work as project, practical exercises in the form of excursions, as well as extensive use of role-playing games, can be called "active" forms of work in the classroom. They contribute to the greatest involvement of students in the learning process, and hence its assimilation. Thanks to this approach, students learn the so-called oral advance, i.e. they memorize and work out grammatically correct phrases to maintain a conversation (ordering a meal in a restaurant, shopping in a store, passing customs control, etc.), while not delving into the grammar itself. We also provide practical lessons with native speakers, since they contribute to the formation of the correct accent and intonation, teach you to perceive speech by ear and will be extremely relevant for overcoming the language barrier.

In addition, the developed course uses some techniques that are also aimed at improving the quality of lessons, the perception of information and, as a result, to increase the motivation of students.

Thus, it can be concluded that the use of these techniques and techniques in ESP lessons contributes to the expansion and deepening of knowledge of the English language at a sufficient level to navigate in the field of tourism and hospitality. The developed methods will be effective for teaching project work skills, developing correct pronunciation, will help students overcome the language barrier and learn to

engage in conversation with foreign guests without embarrassment and awkwardness and maintain a conversation on various topics (about the traditions and culture of the country, about the sights of the city, etc.). For a person planning to link his future with employment in this field of activity, mastering a professional language is relevant and expedient, since tourism is not only a way for a person to know the world, but also the most promising area of the economy, which contributes to the intensification of international contacts and the expansion of intercultural ties.

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